

Polymetallic complexes. Part-LXXXIV : Hexadentate $\text{O} \text{O} \text{N} \text{--} \text{N} \text{O} \text{O}$ donor azodye tetrameric complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}

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Abstract : Twelve tetrameric complexes of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} with two hexadentate (bis-tridentate) $\text{O} \text{O} \text{N} \text{--} \text{N} \text{O} \text{O}$ donor azodye ligands 4,4'-bis-(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-chlorophenylazo)-diphenyl (LH_4) and 4,4'-bis-(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5'-chlorophenylazo)-diphenylmethane ($\text{L}'\text{H}_4$) have been synthesized. The complexes have been characterised by analytical, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, IR, electronic spectra, ESR, NMR and X-ray diffraction (powder pattern) data. Antifungal and antibacterial activity of the ligands and the complexes were also established. The cobalt(II) and nickel(II) complexes are found to be octahedral, copper(II) complexes are distorted octahedral and a tetrahedral stereochemistry has been assigned to zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) complexes.

Keywords : Polymetallic complexes, azodye complexes.

Introduction

The azodyes are found to be chemotherapeutic and antiseptic in nature¹. They also have other varied uses like dyeing food stuffs, preserving food grains² and as redox-indicators. Potentiometric and spectrophotometric studies of metal complexes with azodyes are well known. Keeping this in mind, we are interested in synthesizing multidentate azodyes and their metal chelates in order to throw some light on their molecular structures and antimicrobial activities³.

Results and discussion

The metal complexes reported in Table 1 have the compositions $[\text{M}_4\text{L}/\text{L}'\text{Cl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{12}]$ and $[\text{M}'_4\text{L}/\text{L}'\text{Cl}_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]$ where $\text{M} = \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} ; $\text{M}' = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} ; $\text{LH}_4 = \text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_6$ (Fig. 1) (Found : C, 56.2; H, 2.5; N, 9.7; Cl, 12.4. Calcd. : C, 56.62; H, 2.90; N, 10.16; Cl, 12.88%); $\text{L}'\text{H}_4 = \text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_6$ (Fig. 2) (Found : C, 54.8; H, 2.9; N, 9.5; Cl, 12.1. Calcd. : C, 55.22; H, 3.18; N, 9.91; Cl, 12.56%). All the complexes are amorphous in nature, with high melting points and are insoluble in common organic solvents but feebly soluble in dimethylformamide. The non-electrolytic nature of the complexes is shown by the low conductance values ($4.3\text{--}5.7 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$).

In the IR spectra of the ligands, broad bands are observed at 3435 cm^{-1} (LH_4) and at $2900\text{--}3400 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ ($\text{L}'\text{H}_4$) respectively which may be attributed to intramolecular O—H---N hydrogen bonding. Disappearance of these bands in the metal chelates indicates the bonding of the phenolic -OH groups to the metal atoms. The bands at 1475 cm^{-1} (LH_4) and at 1472 cm^{-1} ($\text{L}'\text{H}_4$) can be attributed to phenolic C—O vibration and in metal chelates these bands appear at $\sim 1447 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicating the bonding of ligands to the metal ions through the phenolic oxygen atoms⁶. The sharp bands for the ligands at 1600 cm^{-1} (LH_4) and 1609 cm^{-1} ($\text{L}'\text{H}_4$) can be assigned to $\gamma_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ vibrations and in the metal complexes these bands appear at $\sim 1565 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which indicates the bonding of one of the azo nitrogen atoms to the metal atoms⁷. In the ligands $\gamma_{\text{as}}(\text{COO}^-)$ and $\gamma_{\text{s}}(\text{COO}^-)$ bands appear at 1657 and 1435 cm^{-1} (LH_4) and 1668 and 1442 cm^{-1} ($\text{L}'\text{H}_4$) respectively and these bands appear in the metal complexes at $\sim 1597\text{--}1599$ and $1426\text{--}1427 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a difference ($\Delta\gamma$) of $\sim 172 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ supporting monodentate nature of the carboxylate group⁸. In the metal chelates, broad bands appear at $\sim 3176\text{--}3349$ and $\sim 3152\text{--}3390 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ followed by sharp peaks at ~ 836 , $\sim 725 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (~ 836 , $\sim 723 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) assignable to OH stretching, rocking and wagging vibrations respectively

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes

Compd.	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)			μ_{eff} (B.M.)
		Metal	Nitrogen	Chlorine	
LH ₄	Reddish brown	–	9.7 (10.16)	12.4 (12.88)	–
L'H ₄	Brown	–	9.5 (9.91)	12.1 (12.56)	–
[Co ₂ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Dark brown	20.2 (20.67)	4.5 (4.91)	18.2 (18.68)	2.5
[Co ₂ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Light brown	20.3 (20.41)	4.4 (4.84)	18.1 (18.44)	2.4
[Ni ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Reddish brown	20.2 (20.59)	4.5 (4.91)	18.2 (18.68)	2.2
[Ni ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Brown	19.9 (20.34)	4.3 (4.85)	18.1 (18.46)	2.3
[Cu ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Light green	21.5 (21.92)	4.4 (4.83)	17.9 (18.37)	1.4
[Cu ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	Grey	21.1 (21.65)	4.3 (4.77)	17.8 (18.15)	1.3
[Zn ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Brown	25.2 (25.57)	5.2 (5.47)	20.4 (20.83)	–
[Zn ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Reddish brown	24.8 (25.23)	5.1 (5.40)	20.2 (20.54)	–
[Cd ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Faint yellow	36.8 (37.13)	4.2 (4.62)	17.1 (17.59)	–
[Cd ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	Dark brown	36.2 (36.71)	4.3 (4.57)	17.1 (17.39)	–
[Hg ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	White	50.8 (51.31)	3.3 (3.58)	13.2 (13.62)	–
[Hg ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	White	50.4 (50.85)	3.2 (3.55)	13.2 (13.50)	–

indicating the presence of co-ordinated water molecules in the complexes⁹. The conclusive evidence of bonding of the ligands to the metal ions is proved by the appearance of bands at ~540 (M–O) and ~490 cm⁻¹ (M–N)¹⁰.

The complexes of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) exhibit sub-normal magnetic moments and could be attributed to the magnetic interaction between the metal ions present in a polymeric structure $M \begin{array}{c} \diagup \\ \text{O} \\ \diagdown \end{array} M^{II}$.

In the electronic spectra of Co^{II} complexes, four ligand field bands are observed at 8242 (8265), 16610 (16725), 20232 (20275) and 32210 (32255) cm⁻¹. The first three bands can be attributed to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$

(γ_1), $\rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (γ_2) and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ (γ_3) transitions respectively and the fourth band is assigned to a CT band. The ligand field parameters like $Dq = 8368$ (8460) cm⁻¹, $B = 807.7$ (813.66) cm⁻¹, $\beta_{35} = 0.831$ (0.837) cm⁻¹, $\gamma_2/\gamma_1 = 2.015$ (2.023) and $\sigma = 20.33\%$ (19.47%) suggest an octahedral geometry for the complexes¹². In the electronic spectra of Ni^{II} complexes, four ligand field bands are observed at 10220 (10258), 17285 (17310), 24985 (24998) and 32690 (32775) cm⁻¹ assignable to ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F)$ (γ_1), $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F)$ (γ_2), $\rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P)$ (γ_3) and CT transition respectively in a distorted octahedral symmetry field. The ligand field parameters like $Dq = 1022$ (1025.8) cm⁻¹, $B = 774.0$ (768.93) cm⁻¹, $\beta_{35} = 0.743$ (0.738) cm⁻¹, $\gamma_2/\gamma_1 = 1.691$

Fig. 1. 4,4'-Bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5-chlorophenylazo)-diphenyl (LH₄).

Fig. 2. 4,4'-Bis(2'-hydroxy-3'-carboxy-5-chlorophenylazo)-diphenylmethane (L'H₄).

Table 2. X-Ray diffraction data of the complex

Compd.	2 θ -Values	Unit cell parameter	Density (g/cc)	<i>n</i>	Possible geometry
[Co ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	10.897, 12.991, 14.935, 16.879,	A = 13.424	0.609	1.0	Hexagonal
	18.973, 20.917, 22.861, 28.993,	B = 15.797			
	30.937, 31.984, 34.862, 36.322,	C = 8.939			
	42.603, 43.949, 44.098, 50.380,	α = 90.000			
	52.623, 53.820, 63.242, 64.887,	β = 90.000			
	72.514, 74.907, 75.057, 82.684,	γ = 90.00			
	82.834, 84.778, 86.722, 87.470,	V = 1895.56			
	90.012				

(1.687) and $\sigma = 34.58\%$ (35.50%) also confirm the octahedral symmetry for the complexes¹³. The electronic spectra of the copper(II) complexes show one broad band at $\sim 13555\text{--}14490\text{ cm}^{-1}$ with maxima at $\sim 14365\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in support of a distorted octahedral configuration of the complexes¹⁴.

The ESR spectra of the copper complexes [Cu₄LCl₄(H₂O)₁₂] and [Cu₄L'₄(H₂O)₁₂] have been recorded at X-band at room temperature. In the first complex, the computation made by Piesach and Blumberg's method suggests the presence of two 'g' values. The geometry around the Cu^{II} ions in the unit cell is tetragonal (elongated octahedral) with $g_{\perp} = 2.0614$ and $g_{\parallel} = 2.12024$. The axial symmetry parameter 'G' is found to be 1.92, which indicates strong exchange interaction among the magnetically equivalent copper(II) ions in the unit cell. The g_{\parallel} is a function for representing covalence. The g_{\parallel} is found

to be less than 2.3, indicating covalent nature of the complex, $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_e$ (2.0023) indicates that the unpaired electron is localised in $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital. The ' g_{av} ' value of the second complex was found to be 2.12129 by Kneubuhl's method. This type of spectrum might be due to dynamic or pseudo rotational behaviour of Jahn-Teller distortion. The covalent nature of M-L bond is indicated from low ' g_{av} ' value (<2.3). This value is in consistent with Cu-O and Cu-N bonded copper complexes¹⁵.

The ¹H NMR spectra of the ligands LH₄ and L'H₄ were recorded in CDCl₃. The complex pattern observed at δ 6.9288–7.9219 (LH₄) and 6.9581–7.8888 (L'H₄) corresponds to 12 phenyl protons on each ligand. The sharp singlet observed at δ 10.3340 (LH₄) and 10.4060 (L'H₄) corresponds to two phenolic protons respectively. The sharp peak observed at δ 2.9618 (L'H₄) correspond to two methylene (-CH₂-) protons¹⁶.

Graph 1. XRD graph for [Co₄L'Cl₄(H₂O)₁₂] complex.

Table 3. Antimicrobial activities of the compounds with their inhibition zones in (nm)

Compd.	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Proteus mirabilis</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>
	ATCC-25923	NCTC-289	ATCC-27853	Van Tieghem
	LH ₄	+	-	-
L'H ₄	+	-	-	-
[Co ₂ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	-	-	-	+
[Co ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	-	-	-	-
[Ni ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	-	-	-	-
[Ni ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	-	-	-	-
[Cu ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	+	-	-	-
[Cu ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₁₂]	+	-	-	++
[Zn ₄ LCl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	+	-	-	++
[Zn ₄ L'Cl ₄ (H ₂ O) ₄]	-	-	-	-

Diameters of the zone of inhibition : (-) resistant (14 mm or less); (+) less active (15–16 mm); (++) moderate active (16–17 mm), the solvent used was DMF.

The XRD studies of the complex [Co₄L'Cl₄(H₂O)₁₂] were made with the help of X-ray diffractometer by powder pattern method and the unit cell parameters were calculated by a computer from the 2θ values (Graph 1). The direct constants of these lattices like *A*, *B*, *C*, α, β, γ and *V* (volume) shown in Table 2 suggest the probable geometry of the complex to be hexagonal. The density (*d*) of the complex was determined by the floatation method in a saturated solution of KBr, NaCl and benzene separately. The number of formula units per unit cell (*n*) is calculated from the relation $n = dNV/M$, where *d* = density of the compound, *N* = Avogadro's number, *V* = volume of the unit cell and *M* = molecular weight of the complex. The value of 'n' is found to be 1.0 for the complex which agrees well with the suggested structure of the complex¹⁷.

The Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are hence suggested to be four-coordinated having tetrahedral geometry based on analytical, conductance and IR spectral data and both the azo dyes behave as hexadentate (bis-tridentate) ligands and form tetrameric complexes with phenolic oxygen bridge.

The biological properties (antibacterial and antifungal) of the ligands and their metal chelates were studied and the results were shown in Table 5. The

levels of antimicrobial activities of the compounds are of three different types i.e. moderately active, less active and not active (resistant).

Experimental

All the chemicals were of B.D.H. or E. Merck grade. The metal, carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and chlorine were estimated by standard methods⁴. Conductivity measurements of the complexes were made using Toshniwal CL01-06 conductivity bridge. The magnetic moments were measured at RT by Gouy method. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded using IFS 66U spectrophotometer, electronic spectra (10⁻² M in DMF) using Hilger-Watt uvispeck spectrophotometer. ESR spectra of copper(II) complexes on a E₄-spectrometer and NMR spectra on a Jeol GSX 400 with CDCl₃ as solvent and TMS as internal standard and X-ray diffraction (powder pattern) of the complex [Co₄L'Cl₄(H₂O)₁₂] was recorded on a Phillip PW 1130 diffractometer.

Preparation of the ligand :

Both azodyes were prepared by the coupling reaction of the diazonium chlorides obtained from benzidine (0.01 mol, 1.84 g) and 4,4'-diaminodiphenylmethane (0.01 mol, 1.98 g) with alkaline solution of 5-chlorosalicylic acid [0.02 mol, 3.44 g (LH₄), 0.02 mol 3.44 g, (L'H₄)] at 0–5 °C.

Preparation of the complexes :

The metal chloride in ethanol was mixed separately with ethanolic solution of the ligands in 4 : 1 molar ratio and the resulting solutions were heated to 50–60 °C for about an hour on a heating mantle. The solution was then cooled down to room temperature and the pH was raised to ~7 by adding conc. ammonia drop by drop with stirring. The solid complexes thus separated were washed with ethanol followed by ether and dried in vacuum.

The biological activity of the ligands and the complexes were determined by the "agar diffusion technique"⁵. The compounds were screened *in vitro* against three strains of bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* (ATCC-25923), *Proteus mirabilis* (NCTC-289) and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (ATCC-27853) and one strain of fungi, *Aspergillus niger* (Van Tieghem). A 1 mg/ml solution in DMF was used. The bacterium was maintained on nutrient agar and the fungus was extracted by pure culture method. The agar media were incubated for different microorganism culture tests. After 24 h of incubation at 37 °C for bacteria and 72 h of incubation at 25 °C for fungi, the diameter of zone of inhibition (mm) were measured and shown in Table 3. Ampicilin was used as reference for antibacterial and streptomycin for antifungal tests.

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